

On the Search for a Foundation

To search for a foundation for ethics is an attempt to be honest toward what already happens to us, without remaining imprisoned by it. It is difficult to prove that the right has an absolute, ontological, or metaphysical origin — as many traditions maintain — but it is just as difficult to deny that it has a deeply human root. We can begin from what we find ourselves feeling, often before we know how to put it into words: not because that feeling is pure or infallible, but because it is the first place where something begins to count. Moral sensibility is not born already just. It takes shape over time, in the encounter with others, but also within fears, defenses, habits, and self-deceptions. In part it comes from ancient dispositions, such as empathy; in part it is learned, by erring and correcting oneself. It is not given once and for all, but neither do I believe it is arbitrary.

A long history, biological and cultural, has left in us traces of varying depth: primary perceptions such as pain and pleasure; basic emotions such as fear or anger; more complex dispositions such as empathy, the need to belong, distrust, the desire to prevail. From this ground rises the voice of the first moral intuitions: no longer merely feeling something, but feeling that something matters or wounds, that life has value in itself. It is moral conscience at its first appearing — instinctive, immediate, before it can even explain itself.

Moral intuitions are precious, but raw: a radar, not a compass. They can signal something that deserves attention, but they can also register an old fear, a habit, a prejudice never questioned. For this reason they should be listened to, not obeyed. And it is not enough to order them coherently: an ordered prejudice is still a prejudice. They must be left exposed to the possibility of being wrong.

This examination passes first of all through reason, which tries to give balance and coherence to those primary intuitions, without which, in any case, one would reason in a void. From what we feel we try to derive principles, and we ask ourselves whether we could want them to hold for others as well, and not only when it suits us.

But coherence is not enough. A noble principle can become cruel if it forgets the flesh-and-blood people to whom it applies. For this reason rules must always return to real life, and be weighed also by the suffering they avoid and the value they make possible. There is here an attention to consequences, but rendered human, not reduced to calculation. I do not oppose duty to consequences: I hold both together. Duty prevents calculation from sacrificing a person; consequences prevent the rule from becoming blind.

Fundamental in this process is the encounter with the other. One cannot decide alone, shut inside one's own head, what is just or better. We need to listen to those who have lived otherwise than we have, above all when the gaze of the person before us cracks what seemed obvious to us. Without the other, one of the decisive tests of judgment is missing: the one that shows what we could not see on our own. This holds above all when the other is affected by the consequences of a norm or a choice: those who suffer a harm, an exclusion, or a form of domination often see something that those who decide from a safer position may not see.

What is born from this is not a pure system. It is a process: what we feel and the reflections we make correct each other through what we live and the people we meet. The more the process remains open and honest, the more solid its conclusions. They do not thereby become definitive certainties: they remain correctable, and it is this exposure to refutation that makes them reliable.

This does not mean that everything counts equally. Some positions, when put to the test, do not hold up: because they contradict what they declare, distort the facts, annul fundamental principles, or fail to consider the complexity of the factors at stake.

One sees this in history as well. Things change: what one age finds natural, another can no longer bear. Not because history always moves toward the better: it also knows long seasons of cruelty, reversals, regressions, collective enthusiasms for what dehumanizes. Cultures and moral intuitions influence one another. Cultures do not shape only external norms: they penetrate into the structure of conscience, refining or clouding what seems spontaneously right to us. But moral intuitions too, when they resist and become articulate, can crack the

received codes and generate change. This is how a society discovers it was wrong; and this is how each of us, on certain days, realizes we have mistaken our own habit for justice.

In this process one might even read a further direction, perhaps glimpsed in fragments in the way civilizations construct and compare their ethics. But it remains a hypothesis, alongside the opposite one of an indifferent, unguided process. For this reason ethics must hold even without that guarantee.

Whatever answer one gives to the question of the ultimate meaning of things, one condition remains: we are all exposed. Sooner or later anyone can be wounded, even those who believe themselves strong. This common fragility does not by itself prove any duty and does not automatically make us better. It can open us to care, but it can also harden us, make us possessive, resentful, eager to control what we fear to lose. It remains, however, the ground from which moral judgment can set out. It is not a proof; it is a recognition.

To place vulnerability at the center does not mean making fragility an ideal, nor preferring weakness to strength. It means recognizing that every human strength remains exposed, dependent, woundable, and that precisely for this reason it needs measure. Even freedom, without this recognition, can turn into indifference toward what makes the lives of others possible.

What is described here is a recognizable orientation, not a demonstrable theorem. Care can be misunderstood or corrupted, like every human value. When it becomes control, possession, or the need to save the other at all costs, it ceases to be care and becomes a softer form of domination. When instead it recognizes the other as a center of experience and not as an object of our protection, it is neither weakness nor consolation: it is the attempt to stand before fragility without immediately turning it into possession.

From here also arises the way in which I can speak of the good. No one possesses the Good with a capital G, as an already defined absolute that someone could hold and impose. One can instead find a smaller good: a direction, not a possession. It is recognized when a suffering is relieved, a person respected, a possibility restored.

These are truths with a lowercase "t": not mere opinions, but historical acquisitions, incomplete, exposed to new facts and other experiences; revisable, and for this very reason more robust than a dogma. They are not enough on their own to build an entire ethics, but they offer some of its cornerstones. That pain is lived as pain by the one who feels it, or that a humiliation is suffered by the one who undergoes it, are facts of experience before being judgments about it. From this it does not yet automatically follow what duty derives for others; but without that lived pain there would not even be anything to recognize, interpret, or protect. The moral conclusion comes afterward: it interprets what happens, universalizes it, considers its consequences, listens to other points of view. It is lowercase not because everything is relative, but because our ways of recognizing, formulating, and applying it are fallible. Dogmatic hardening is dangerous precisely because it rules out from the start the possibility of being wrong.

In this sense, choosing ethically does not mean applying an algorithm. It means exercising a difficult art of judgment: seeking a balance among feeling, principles, consequences, concrete lives, and particular cases, knowing that what is best or right does not always allow itself to be calculated, but must be recognized, discussed, and corrected. Sometimes, in fact, it is not a matter of choosing between a good and an evil, but among different goods that come into tension. No recognized value should claim to absorb all the others: even what is just, if it forgets measure, can become hard, blind, even violent.

The most elementary ground that can be recognized is not yet a moral principle, but life. Not life as pure biology, nor a life to be celebrated no matter what, but the life that feels: the life for which there exists a point of view, and for which what happens can become pain or joy. It is not the mere being alive that deserves respect. It is the fact that, within a life, something can be felt by someone.

This feeling is not isolated. Every life is born within relationships that sustain or wound it. We are points of view, but not points separated from the world. We recognize more easily a center of experience in those who resemble us, and with growing uncertainty in beings progressively more distant from us. But this is a difficulty

of our gaze, not a measure of their feeling: resemblance to us makes experience easier to recognize, not more real.

The life that feels is the point from which we know, because everything we know, we know by living. It is the point at which the world becomes present, lived. And it is the point from which what has value, what is just, carries weight — because a weight is always a weight for someone. To say this is not to say that life is good merely because it is life. Life can also wound and dominate, and mere existence does not make a form of existence just. One can say, however, that the life that feels is the condition for something to be given to us as lived good or evil — not the final proof that it has value.

Where there is a life that feels, the world does not merely happen: it happens for someone. A stone can break, but it cannot be wounded; there is no one for whom that fracture is a loss. In a life that feels, by contrast, damage is not merely an external modification: it becomes evil for someone.

Moral judgment comes afterward. It interprets that experience, relates it to that of others, tries to establish what it demands. It can understand it badly, can distort it, can absolutize it. But it does not create from nothing the fact that something was suffered or lost.

This is a statement about life capable of experience even before it is a statement about moral language. Pain, joy, and loss possess a lived direction prior to judgment: they are not yet a moral law, but neither are they morally mute facts. Value therefore seems to me neither a mysterious thing placed outside the world, nor a purely private projection. For us it is given in the relation between a world and a point of view capable of being touched by it. That pain is lived by a subject does not make it arbitrary: it makes it real for someone.

One might put happiness first, or pleasure, or the absence of pain; or duty, reason, freedom. But these values too acquire weight only within a life for which something can matter. The life that feels is not one value alongside the others: it is the place where happiness, pain, duty, freedom, and reason can become meaningful for someone.

And there is something paradoxical in this condition. Useful things have value with a view to an end; but the things we love most — beauty, a gesture made for nothing — serve no other purpose: they are themselves the end. Life is "useless" in the same way: it does not take its value from a purpose outside itself, because it is within a life capable of experience that every purpose begins, for us, to make sense. And what matters then is not only avoiding pain. Life does not ask only not to suffer: it asks also to bind itself to someone, to be able to express itself. Evil is not only suffering: it is also being made invisible. And the good is not only the absence of evil: it is being able to live more fully, without this passing through the ruin of another.

If the most elementary ground from which to begin is the life that feels, the method by which we transform that ground into judgment is the fallible interweaving of intuition, reason, consequences, and listening. The recognition of vulnerability as a common condition does not by itself produce an entire morality, but it orients certain fundamental values: dignity, respect, recognition, care, freedom, responsibility, justice, solidarity. In different ways, all of them arise from the fact that a life capable of feeling cannot be treated as a thing, ignored in its fragility, or left alone in the conditions that expose it.

It is not a demonstrated point of arrival. In searching for a foundation one finds something less rigid than a pillar and more solid than an opinion: an orientation. It rests on the recognition of oneself and of the other, and it remains reliable only as long as it accepts being corrected.

Note on the Foundation as Orientation

In this note I make explicit the method that the preceding section leaves implicit, and I argue for the thesis that takes shape in it: ethics does not need an ultimate foundation to escape arbitrariness. It can hold as a fallible but robust orientation, built from the life that feels and from the vulnerability we share, tested by reason, measured against consequences, corrected in the encounter with those who see what I do not see. The references have names and histories — reflective equilibrium, constructivism, sentientism, value pluralism — but here I do not

assume them as closed doctrines: I weave them together as resources for thinking an ethics that is neither dogmatic nor relativist. The thread that holds these references together is simple: value announces itself in experience, is corrected by method, finds in sentient life its minimal threshold, and remains exposed, in real conflicts, to the pluralism of goods and to the residue of what cannot be saved.

The method is a form of reflective equilibrium, in its wide version.^[^1] I do not start from absolute principles already given, nor from emotions taken as infallible, but from more human material: primary sensations, emotions, moral intuitions, immediate reactions before pain or injustice. This material is raised to principle — I ask whether what I feel could hold not only for me — and brought back to consequences: what it produces in real life, whom it protects and whom it wounds, what possibilities it opens or closes. Finally it is exposed to the encounter with other gazes, above all those that contradict me. What gives the method its strength is precisely its fallibility: no step is untouchable, and not only a conclusion but even a starting intuition can fall. It is not a rigid ladder, where first comes feeling, then reason, then consequences, then dialogue: the moments interweave, and sometimes an unforeseen consequence forces the revision of a principle, a criticism shows that an intuition was only fear or privilege, a concrete case obliges one to reformulate everything.

Why start from intuitions, if they are often unreliable? It is worth first agreeing on the term. A primary sensation such as pain, an affective capacity such as empathy, and the immediate apprehension that something not only happens but matters — that it is to be avoided, sought, protected, or understood — can be distinguished in analysis, but they do not always present themselves to lived experience already separated. Often they arrive as a single pre-reflective configuration, in which feeling and orientation are interwoven before ever becoming principle.

Pain is not first suffered and then judged an evil: it is suffered-as-to-be-avoided in a single movement of experience. The joy of an encounter is not first felt and then judged a good: it is lived-as-to-be-sought in the very moment it happens. Empathy and identification — the capacity to remain emotionally open to the other, so that their feeling makes ours vibrate — are the sensible root of recognition. The pain and joy of others cease to be an external fact and become something that concerns me: the other reveals themselves, at least initially, as a center of experience similar to me. I call intuitions this ensemble of pre-reflective evaluative apprehensions, to which we are often so accustomed that we no longer see their structure.^[^2] They are not already justified judgments, nor infallible moral truths. They are rather the first way in which the world appears to us as meaningful. Precisely because they arrive before analysis, they can contain different elements together: a real vulnerability, an empathic response, a fear, a habit, a cultural inheritance, a partial perspective. Rational scrutiny then serves to disentangle after the fact what experience initially presents interwoven: to distinguish what deserves trust from what must be corrected, what expresses a real wound from what repeats a distortion.

Why then start from intuitions? Because without a first moral feeling we would not even have anything to reason about. Reason, separated from all lived experience, remains empty: logic can show contradictions, universalization can test a rule, calculation can measure consequences; but none of these instruments decides by itself what counts. Even the test that asks whether a rule could hold for everyone presupposes, in order to work, what it seems to derive. When I universalize a maxim and reject it because it would lead to a world I could not will — at the limit, the extinction of humanity — it is because I have already assumed that this outcome is a loss. The contradiction the test brings out does not by itself create the value: it brings it to light, orders it, puts it to the test. Without a minimal intuition establishing that certain outcomes matter, formal coherence alone would not yet tell us which side to stand on.

It is worth then drawing the implicit consequence from all this. Every time that, among rival foundations, I tip the scale to one side, what tips it is never abstract reason alone: it is always, upstream, an intuition that recognizes something as value. Among rival foundations — pleasure, duty, freedom, life, the order of the world, knowledge, beauty, salvation — reason does not elect a criterion out of nothing. It can clarify, order, show strength or fragility, but it always works within a horizon in which something has already begun to matter. Those who choose pleasure and those who choose duty do not simply commit, relative to each other, an error of logic. They make a different ordinary valuation: they feel, before they can prove it, that there lies what deserves to be saved. The same holds for those who consider life sacred in every form and for those who place above it freedom, justice, conscience, dignity, or something else: no one deduces their measure entirely from pure inference; they assume it because something, in that measure, appears to them as what matters.

This does not mean that all foundations are equivalent. Once they have entered the moral field, they must still answer to coherence, to consequences, to reciprocity, to confrontation with experience, to the possibility of being shared without violence or contradiction. Some values reveal themselves more capable of including, correcting, and making life habitable; others show their partial, destructive, or sterile character. But the first access to value does not arise from the form of reasoning alone. Even those who claim to start from pure reason, or from pure calculation, have already made a preliminary choice: logic and computation work afterward, on an end they have not given themselves.

Intuition is therefore not only the raw material from which I begin and which I will have to correct. It is the access without which a value would not enter the field at all, though it is not yet its completed form. Reason clarifies it, makes it coherent, compares it with other values, measures its consequences, seeks its contradictions; dialogue corrects it, experience scales it down, and only in this work does value take shape.

But precisely because it is necessary, intuition is also dangerous: it can be partial, interested, deformed by fear, habit, or privilege. For this reason it cannot have the last word. Reason corrects its partiality, consequences its abstractness, dialogue its closure. None of these steps, alone, guarantees truth; together they build a correction that does not answer to arbitrariness.

It will be said, then, that if the starting intuitions are distorted, making them coherent does not make them true: garbage in, garbage out.^[^3] The objection is right, but it strikes a closed reflective equilibrium, one that orders the initial intuitions without putting them in danger. It strikes far less a wide equilibrium, where intuitions can be refuted by consequences and by the human sciences, by the analysis of power relations, by the critical examination of the intuitions themselves, and above all by the voice of those who suffer what I, from where I stand, do not see. The same difficulty, in a deeper form, is the Darwinian dilemma: if our intuitions are products of evolution, their coherence guarantees no access to independent values.^[^4] The answer does not consist in refuting the dilemma, nor in taking refuge in constructivism as if that sufficed. It consists in scaling down the claim. Mine is not a refutation of realism, but an epistemic position: whatever value may be in itself, the only evaluative access we have passes through intuitions — reason, by itself, would not know which of rival value-postulates to elect, and would fall back into the undecidability the Münchhausen trilemma describes. Intuition is what breaks that symmetry, because it is the only point at which a valuation presents itself instead of being postulated; but it is a necessary access, not a sufficient one: precisely because it was forged by evolution and culture, it is not good a priori, and it must be scrutinized, compared among the others, made coherent, measured against consequences and against applicability to real cases.

Street is right that, on their own, intuitions do not guarantee an independent truth; but from this it follows neither that there exists another way of accessing it that bypasses them, nor that independent truths do not exist. There remains open, therefore, the possibility that, through scrutiny, intuitions do not merely construct a value but come to grasp a real one: it is the door toward realism that Street would like to bar and that I leave ajar — knowing that, even if beyond that door there were an independent value, one would still reach it through intuitions, reasoning, and dialogue. Metaphysical suspension does not paralyze the method: it shows that ethics can be thought without deciding once and for all whether value is discovered, constructed, or emergent in relation. In any case, our access passes through intuitions, reasoning, consequences, and dialogue. When a conclusion holds — it is coherent, practicable, capable of standing before those who suffer its effects, and proves sustainable over time — its holding does not prove that it grasps that truth, but it corroborates its validity: it is the only solidity to which a fallible orientation can aspire, not the certainty of having seen rightly, but having withstood the tests that could have refuted it. And the fact that our intuitions come from far back does not make them merely suspect: it roots them in a process that, whatever ultimate origin — of chance or of design — one wishes to attribute to it, remains ancestrally part of us.

Even the Münchhausen trilemma, then, does not refute ethics: it shows within what limits every justification moves.^[^5] In this framework its three horns are not eliminated: they are assumed as three sides of a single movement. The regress preserves the genealogical depth of the question: reasons refer back to the intuitions that generated them, and these to a biological and cultural genealogy that recedes backward in time, as far as knowledge reaches — and this prevents presenting as pure what has a history. But, without a foundational certainty, ascending that chain still leaves open the possibility that, at its end, there is a deeper, metaphysical origin — real and independent of us — to which the method may gain access, though without the certainty that

it is there, nor that it has truly been reached. And the same fallibility that holds for conclusions holds also for the criteria by which they are weighed. Not only intuitions, principles, and applications can be corrected: so can the way we understand coherence, consequences, listening to the other, concrete cases, and universalization. Even the measuring rod, then, is not withdrawn from the movement it measures. The circle is fruitful all the way down only if it includes its own criteria: if it corrects not only what it weighs, but also the way it weighs. And here too it remains possible that this mutual correcting does not spin idly upon itself — that the process by which we construct our truths, or perhaps gain access to them, is not a closed circle but a spiral, and that this spiral is not merely the form of our proceeding, but a figure perhaps already inscribed in reality. It is not demonstrable, and it is not excluded; and the fallibility of the process must in any case always be kept in mind, as a caution against the possible regressions or errors that the scrutiny itself can bring with it. The halt is inevitable in action: to orient myself and to act I need to be able to take a position, to set my foot down somewhere; and one can stop on truths with a lowercase "t" — necessary but not definitive, always revisable, and not for that reason less solid or more arbitrary than the recognition of not being able to dispose with certainty of an ultimate foundation allows. The halt is not then a surrender, but the form that taking a position assumes when it has stopped claiming certainties it cannot have. And of this halt too it remains possible that the point on which I set my foot is not merely where I chose to stop asking, but the tending-toward, or the attempt to recognize, something real — not only something constructed out of our subjectivity or our intersubjectivity. It is not demonstrable, and it is not excluded. What I was seeking as a foundation reveals itself as a structured, non-arbitrary orientation.[^6]

Arbitrariness is avoided not because the method possesses an ultimate guarantee, but because every step remains exposed to a test. A conviction can contradict itself, rest on false facts, produce consequences that belie what it promised, fail to hold before the life of those who suffer its effects. And the point from which ethical reflection sets out is not an isolated preference, but the always fallible recognition that something in experience presents itself as meaningful.

From here it is necessary to restate what the method can say and what it must leave open. It affirms something about how we access value, not about what value is, nor where it lies, nor whether it exists beyond every point of view capable of grasping it. On this I remain suspended. One thing, however, can be said without overstepping that limit: value always gives itself to us as value-for-a-living-being. We do not encounter it as an isolated property of things, but within a relation between a world and a point of view capable of being touched by it.[^7] To say value-for-a-living-being does not mean reducing value to the living being's preference. It means that value, in order to appear as lived good or evil, requires a center of experience capable of accessing it. Whether that value is already present in the world and merely grasped, whether it is constructed by the gaze, or whether it emerges in the relation between living being and world, remains open; its phenomenological aspect, by contrast, is difficult to call into doubt.[^8]

It is then necessary to distinguish three levels of this relation. The first is lived valence: pain, loss, joy, desire, recognition are not neutral states to which a label of value is later attached, but ways in which the world already happens well or badly for the one who lives them. This is not yet moral judgment, nor norm; it is the minimal point at which something ceases to be indifferent.

The second level is interpretation: where a living being is capable of it, that valence is recognized, articulated, compared with other experiences, made clearer or deeper. Judgment does not create value from nothing: it interprets what in experience already presents itself as meaningful, puts it to the test, and can bring it closer to a more articulated form of value; but it is not for that reason certain of grasping a real independent value, nor is it immune from misunderstanding it.[^9]

There remains, finally, the passage to the norm. Judgment does not derive the norm from value by simple deduction: even when something presents itself as meaningful, it remains to be established what obligation derives from it, how much it should weigh for others, and what conduct is right in the concrete case. This passage is not deduced, but posited through a reasoned recognition, supported by several converging sources. [^10]

Of this living being that feels, without which no value would be recognized, it must now be said what its existential condition is: that it is finite, and vulnerable — exposed with respect to everything to which it gives

value, including its own existence. Recognizing this is the point from which an ethics can begin to move — not a deduced truth, but a recognition, the first to which to apply the method. The starting intuition — that pain matters, mine as much as the other's; that the life that feels has value, in the one who lives it and in the one we encounter, in whom we recognize someone who lives and feels, not something; that what we hold dear asks to be defended — is raised to principle: that the vulnerability of every being that feels asks to be taken into account. Whoever gives importance to something, including themselves, is thereby exposed to the possibility of losing it and to the necessity of defending it. And it holds up even when we look at the values it is supposed to defend: freedom matters for one who can be coerced, joy for one who can suffer its lack, the bond for one who can lose and be lost. What, then, would value be for a being that can lose nothing? Of a being, or a world, entirely invulnerable we have no direct knowledge; but perhaps, with respect to it, it would make no sense to speak of value — at least not in the sense we give it, we vulnerable beings.^[^11] Vulnerability is not, then, one value among others, but what the others presuppose, for us, in order to have any grip. Consequences too confirm this direction: a world that recognizes the vulnerability of its living beings, instead of exploiting it, proves more habitable for all, because trust, promise, cooperation, even fair conflict exist only where the other is not reduced to an instrument.

Against this background, to recognize in the other someone for whom things can go well or badly means recognizing that what touches their existence, their experience, and their possibility of having a world does not thereby become the priority always and everywhere, but is the first place to which judgment must answer. Vulnerability, here, does not mean only fragility of the body or exposure to death: it means exposure in everything that can matter for a living being — bonds, freedom, recognition, the possibility of expressing oneself, the continuity of one's own life. A life capable of value is, for that very reason, exposed to the loss of what has value for it. Feeling thus lets itself be recognized as the center of access to value; and since in it good and evil happen for someone, it is recognized also as the minimal threshold of moral status in the strong sense.^[^12] The choice of sentience, and not of biological life as such, in any case leaves open the question of the value of non-sentient life.^[^13] From here arises the demand for a norm: respect for the vulnerability proper to the sentient being. These considerations do not ground the norm demonstratively, but posit it, through a reasoned recognition, as an orientation of which even those who deny it continue to make use.

Sentience opens moral status; vulnerability describes the condition of the sentient; reflection and dialogue transform this into recognition and into obligations.^[^14] From here no complete morality descends ready-made, but certain cornerstones take shape. The first is dignity, or at least a minimal threshold of it: not to reduce to a thing one who has a point of view, not to treat as available material a center of experience for whom things can go well or badly. It is a truth with a lowercase "t" — declared, not deduced from a metaphysical order — but assumed as a cornerstone, because rooted in the condition we share and capable of withstanding the test. The second is care: the way of standing before the other's fragility without turning it into domination. The other values that are usually listed — respect, the reduction of suffering — are not added as separate items: they are its articulations. To respect is already to recognize dignity; to reduce avoidable suffering is already care in its most immediate form. On the historical and political plane, fundamental rights can be read as the public and institutional form of this threshold: they do not by themselves ground dignity, but they seek to make it enforceable.^[^15]

Dignity and care do not eliminate the weight of consequences. Dignity, or the minimal threshold it indicates, functions as a primary constraint: it prevents treating a sentient life as simply available material. But under that constraint consequences truly count: an abstract norm that produces avoidable pain must be reconsidered. I do not propose a theoretical fusion of deontology and consequentialism, but a practical integration: the principle prevents calculation from making a life available; consequences prevent the principle from becoming blind. There is no precise exchange rate between dignity and consequences: the threshold is not a number, but a zone of deliberation in which judgment takes responsibility for the conflict.^[^16]

This does not mean that every life that feels counts in the same way, or must be treated in the same way. It is useful to distinguish moral status from the profile of goods. Status is the fact that a being counts, that it cannot be treated as a mere thing. Sentience opens it as a threshold: either a being is capable of living something as good or bad for itself, or it is not. The profile is what can go well or badly for that living being, which goods are accessible to its form of life and how much is at stake for it. A being capable of a complex relation to its own future, of lasting bonds it can lose, of memory and expectations possesses goods different from those of a being

whose experience is predominantly tied to present states. The threshold of moral status is not graduated: where there is experience, there is someone who counts. What is graduated is the profile of goods, that is, what can be wounded, deprived, or lost according to the form of life.[¹⁷] This does not make living beings with less complex profiles more available: it means that formally similar harms — deprivation, confinement, separation, death — strike different goods and weigh differently according to the form of life involved.

The profile does not concern only isolated individuals: goods take shape, are transformed, or come under threat within relations of care, dependence, belonging. The relation does not create the living being's value from nothing — if a being feels, there already exists someone for whom things go well or badly, prior to any recognition — but it modifies the concrete profile of the goods at stake and the responsibilities of those who take part in it. Whoever makes a living being dependent on themselves, takes on its care, or stably determines its conditions does not thereby acquire a broader right to dispose of it: they take on obligations and responsibilities. The relation binds the stronger party; it does not authorize them.[¹⁸] To this is added concrete potentiality: not just any abstract possibility, and not a title that the future would confer already now, but the presence of goods not yet exercised or the recoverability of goods temporarily suspended, as in the newborn or in one momentarily deprived of consciousness.[¹⁹]

This gradation does not institute a scale among persons: it distinguishes needs, not holders of status. Different beings, and the same person in different conditions, are vulnerable in different ways and can lose different things; recognizing this does not serve to give less to the more fragile, but to give them what they actually need. It holds also in the opposite direction: different forms of life are not exposed to the same goods nor to the same harms. Judgment must then ask what can be wounded, deprived, or lost in that specific experience; but this difference concerns the form of the attention owed, not the value of the one who receives it, nor their greater or lesser sacrificability. Status, as long as there is an inside to experience, remains whole: what varies is the profile of what can be protected or lost, not the weight of the one who suffers it. And since estimating how much another feels is uncertain, where their experience is hard to reach the burden falls not on the one asking for more consideration, but on the one who would grant less. To treat identically those who have different needs is not equality; it is the gentle way of abandoning the most exposed: the gradation of goods thus works for equity, not against it.

How far this threshold holds in extreme cases — where it is the person themselves who no longer wishes to prolong their own life — is a delicate question, requiring its own cautions and a dedicated treatment.[²⁰]

One understands, then, why the starting point must be the life that feels and not one of the goods it makes possible. Happiness, pleasure, love, knowledge are contents of experience: they always have value for someone, and making them the foundation forgets the living being for whom they matter. Hedonism makes pleasure the sole good, but the "experience machine" shows that we do not want only to feel pleasant states: we truly want to do, to know, to bind ourselves.[²¹] By the opposite route, making the absence of suffering the sole criterion overturns itself: if the only evil were suffering, one would arrive at the paradoxical outcome that the painless annihilation of all sentient life would appear as the highest good.[²²] Reason, duty, and responsibility are instead capacities, and they too presuppose a subject: a duty is a duty for someone. But there is more: if rationality became the criterion of moral status, it would leave at the margins precisely those who feel but do not fully reason — animals, newborns, the cognitively fragile. It is the limit forcefully shown to those ethics that ground dignity on rationality and on reciprocity among equals, and that end up confining the most vulnerable "at the frontiers of justice." To put feeling at the center is at once deeper and more inclusive.

The path proposed here does not arbitrarily privilege the human species: entry into moral space depends on the presence of a center of experience, not on biological membership nor on already having entered into relation with us. A wild animal never encountered is not available material merely because it does not belong to our community or cannot reciprocate. Sentience establishes that there exists someone for whom things can go well or badly; the form of life and concrete relations help determine what, concretely, is good or bad for it. From that moment the burden changes direction: it is not enough to observe that the being belongs to another species or possesses less intelligence; one must show why that difference is pertinent to the fact that it can be wounded. The question "why include it?" receives a first answer from its experience; it then becomes legitimate to ask those who would exclude it by what reason that experience should not count. A practical problem remains: the threshold can be sharp in principle yet blurred in ascertainment — animals distant from us, forms of life

difficult to interpret, perhaps one day non-biological intelligences.[^23] Uncertainty does not make the criterion useless: it imposes caution, and where there are serious reasons to think a being may feel, the burden of proof should not fall on those who ask for inclusion.[^24]

At this point the problem is no longer only to establish a principle, but to judge within conflicts in which several goods can be real and yet incompatible. Care can come into tension with freedom, justice with forgiveness, truth with compassion.[^25] Moral conflict does not always simply oppose a good to an evil: often it opposes different goods, each of which retains a share of reason. For this reason judging is not mechanically applying a formula, but exercising a form of practical wisdom: seeing the particular, recognizing who suffers, understanding which good risks being most gravely betrayed, and taking on the weight of what cannot be saved.

Fundamental goods are multiple, real, and sometimes incompatible, and not always reducible to a common measure. The value sacrificed does not thereby become false: it remains as residue, as loss, and for this reason the right choice is not always innocent.[^26] This residue does not absolve the one who chooses; it obliges them: it demands reducing the harm as far as possible, not repeating the choice lightly, changing, where one can, the conditions that made it necessary. A residue that changes nothing in subsequent conduct would not be recognition, but sentimentalism. A value that claims to absorb all the others easily becomes violent: care becomes control, freedom indifference, justice vengeance. This pluralism is not relativism: the ethical process continues to exclude what is incoherent, impracticable, or incapable of holding before the life of those who suffer its effects; incommensurability concerns only the residue of goods that have passed the test and that, precisely for this reason, cannot be dismissed as mere errors. How this structure measures itself against the cases in which tension becomes tragic — the conflict between lives, the guilty and the victim, what no norm can render painless — is matter deserving a more thorough treatment. Here it is enough to have fixed its form: a primary constraint, not a blind absolute.

An orientation like this can be bent precisely in its most delicate distinctions. The gradation of the profile can become the way of saying that some lives count less, when it should indicate only what is at stake for each. The balancing can become a permission to dispose of a life, when it should measure goods without erasing the threshold. The residue can shrink to a harmless regret, when it should oblige one to reduce the harm and to change, where possible, the conditions that made it necessary. For this reason the openness of the method is not discretion: it remains bound to the fact that every life that feels counts, that vulnerability calls forth a responsibility in those who can protect it without turning protection into domination, and that every sacrifice leaves a debt.

Holding these constraints firm does not, however, eliminate all the hard cases. There are arrangements and relations difficult to evaluate with a clear-cut judgment: because they contain a mutual benefit, however asymmetric, which precisely in its asymmetry demands to be justified; because a long cultural inertia operates within them; or simply because their weave resists a precise boundary line. In certain historical and material conditions some practices may prove still difficult to abandon or to judge with an immediate prohibition; not, however, as what is exempted from the constraint, but as what crosses it leaving a debt, recognizing the tragedy and sacrifice it contains, and remaining turned toward forms that one day might no longer require it. Holding those constraints firm, then, does not mean hardening them into prohibitions that ignore the case. But neither is this openness discretion: it passes through the same ethical process that holds for everything else — universalization, consequences, the weight of the bonds in which every life is embedded, the encounter with those who suffer its effects — and this is what prevents it from becoming either a dogma that does not see persons or a permission that absolves itself.

To say that vulnerability calls forth a responsibility in those who can protect it leaves a difficulty in shadow. To protect is not an inert gesture: it requires the capacity to oppose, to restrain, to make a limit hold — a force, then, and not merely a good disposition. To call it power is uncomfortable, because the word carries its reverse with it: domination, the reduction of the other to a means. The hesitation is understandable, and in part salutary: the force that protects is never entirely safe from that reverse, and the one who protects can, at times, begin to dispose of the one they protect. But precisely for this reason the answer is not to distrust force as such — without it, the duty to protect would remain a mere word — but to distinguish, and to keep the difference under watch: between a force that binds itself to the vulnerability it encounters and one that makes use of it. The

problem is not to pretend that protection can do without force, but to bind every exercise of force to the vulnerability it claims to defend: to ensure that force does not draw from the other's fragility a title to dispose of them, but the limit of its own legitimacy.

Everything said so far, however, must reckon with the reality of things. The process I describe here almost never unfolds freely: it finds before it arrangements in which domination has installed itself and endures, and in which the mechanisms that should correct it are blocked — by the interest of those who exercise it, by an order that makes it appear natural, by the inertia of what has always been done. And the blockage is not only outside us: to see the harm in which one participates means accepting having to change it, and consciousness defends itself by not seeing — out of fear, out of weariness, so as not to find oneself isolated from those around us. The orientation does not fail because it is weak, but because it meets resistance outside and inside the one who should carry it out.[²⁷]

There remain the interlocutors who reject the orientation from the outset, and with them I have no proof that compels from a neutral point. I can, however, show that the negation takes different forms, not all equally coherent. Whoever seriously formulates the thesis that nothing matters does not emit a mere sound: they present a reason and demand that it be understood and evaluated. In this act they already recognize a minimal normative space — a difference between understanding and misunderstanding, between answering a reason and ignoring it — and thus they have already abandoned absolute nihilism.[²⁸] They could renounce even this claim and use language only as an instrument of power: but then they would no longer be offering an argument against ethics; they would be trying to produce an effect. It is the same dependence that unmasks the free rider, the one who enjoys the goods of the common world without paying their price. I do not have a definitive refutation in the sense of a neutral, compelling proof — that would require the very ultimate foundation which cannot be definitively reached — but I can show the internal cost of their position: it is neither free of charge nor symmetrical to mine. Whoever treats every relation as an instrument does not receive trust, they simulate it; they are not recognized, they obtain a counterfeit of recognition. And in order to exist as an exception they need others not to be exceptions: they live only within a world that others make habitable. It is not an alternative to the orientation I propose, but a niche disguised as sovereignty — the same dependence that, already in the argument on vulnerability, domination pays without noticing.

With Nietzsche the confrontation is harder. He suspects that an ethics of compassion is not love of life, but resentment in disguise: the way the weak transform their impotence into a moral measure and call strength "evil." The critique must be taken seriously, and in part I accept it: a care born of envy or of the need for superiority can indeed become domination, and Nietzsche serves to prevent care from being complacent about itself. But his genealogy, however powerful, is not a demonstrated fact: it is an interpretation, the mirror image of mine. He can read care as masked power, just as I can read oppression as masked fear; neither proves itself. The difference lies elsewhere: care, when it is neither flight from conflict nor need for superiority, is itself a form of strength — if value is born from measuring oneself against a resistance, to withstand illness, dependence, and the other's fragility without using them to raise oneself is anything but weakness.[²⁹] Nor is attention to fragility incompatible with the full expression of oneself. To recognize one's own and others' vulnerability does not mean making caution the supreme value: fullness does not coincide with oppression, and the affirmation of life does not require contempt for what is fragile. And a world of pure domination consumes the very conditions in which even strength has meaning: trust, promise, knowledge, even fair conflict exist only where the other is not always reduced to a threat. I do not choose care because it is more tender, but because a world without care erodes the very freedom it claims to exalt. This does not convert the coherent Nietzschean, who may accept living beyond that pact; it shows, however, that care is not a consolatory value, but a condition of the common world, and thus of freedom itself. Here the answer on vulnerability and the reply to the radical interlocutors coincide: integral domination is not only morally questionable, it consumes the relational conditions that make possible even the strength it claims to affirm.

In the end the thesis remains modest in its claim and precise in its structure. The life that feels, vulnerable and relational, is the place through which value appears to us: the point at which a world happens for someone and can be lived as good or evil. It is not assumed as a demonstrable good, nor guaranteed as an independent metaphysical property, nor reduced to a subjective projection — on all of this one has chosen to remain suspended, because it is more honest than feigning a certainty one does not have. But the suspension does not leave one empty-handed. From that place one derives a threshold — where there is experience, there is

someone for whom things matter — and a method for crossing it without arbitrariness: intuition that opens access, reason that corrects it, consequences that measure it, dialogue that exposes it to what we cannot see on our own. None of these steps is an ultimate foundation; taken together, they do something an ultimate foundation could not do better: withstand the tests that could have refuted them.

This is what one gains when one renounces certainty. The trilemma that seemed to condemn every ethics to arbitrariness turns over into the three sides of a single movement: the question that ascends backward without end, the circle in which every element corrects the others, the foot that at a certain point comes to rest. Whether at the end of that ascent there truly is an independent value, or only our best-constructed work, remains undecidable from this side of our access; and ethics does not need it in order to hold, because in either case one would arrive there by the same route: intuitions scrutinized, principles corrected, voices heard.

What I was seeking as a foundation then reveals itself as an orientation: not a fallback with respect to the missing foundation, but the form that taking a position assumes when it has stopped claiming what it cannot have, and does not for that reason surrender to arbitrariness. Whoever wants to exclude from moral space a being that feels must still explain why that center of experience should not count — and will not be able to do so by appealing to species, strength, or convenience alone. What remains is a way of walking; but walking, here, is not the opposite of standing. It is what one does when the ground holds at every step precisely because no step claims to be the last.

[^1]: The notion of reflective equilibrium is J. Rawls's, *A Theory of Justice* (1971); the "wide" version (wide reflective equilibrium), which exposes intuitions not only to internal coherence but to background theories, empirical facts, and alternative perspectives, is elaborated above all by N. Daniels, "Wide Reflective Equilibrium and Theory Acceptance in Ethics" (1979). It is to the latter that I refer: without the opening to background theories, the method would remain exposed to the objection recalled in the following note.

[^2]: The description of moral judgment as predominantly intuitive, rapid, and affective — with reasoning often serving as subsequent justification — is at the center of J. Haidt's "social intuitionist model," "The Emotional Dog and Its Rational Tail" (*Psychological Review* 108, 2001), which ties it to culture, education, and experience, and holds it to be revisable through dialogue and reflection. I assume this descriptive datum without the stronger thesis, sometimes associated with that model, which reduces reason to mere rationalization: here reflection does not only explain the intuition after the fact, but can correct it. The term acquires, moreover, a more demanding sense in classical ethical intuitionism (G. E. Moore, W. D. Ross), where intuition is the faculty that grasps non-natural moral truths: a realist position I do not share in its strongest form, but one that grasps something true — that before certain things the recognition of their value precedes every argument. There intuition tends to guarantee an access to the true; here it remains fallible material to be scrutinized; and yet, in both senses, it retains a common trait: it precedes reason, it does not derive from it. Whether in this preceding something true is really grasped, or only the sediment of our history, is a question that remains open here; but to precede is not yet to be valid, and in neither answer is intuition exempted from scrutiny, nor, by the mere fact of coming first, already in the right.

[^3]: "Garbage in, garbage out" is the formula summarizing the classic objection to reflective equilibrium: ordering distorted intuitions does not correct them. The criticism, advanced among others by R. B. Brandt (*A Theory of the Good and the Right*, 1979) and R. M. Hare, and taken up forcefully by P. Singer ("Ethics and Intuitions", *The Journal of Ethics* 9, 2005), is that the method merely systematizes the starting prejudices. The answer lies not in coherence, but in exposing intuitions to what does not depend on them — consequences, the human sciences, the voice of those who suffer.

[^4]: S. Street, "A Darwinian Dilemma for Realist Theories of Value", *Philosophical Studies* (2006). The dilemma presents the realist with a choice between two horns, both losing. Our evaluative tendencies have been shaped by selection, which rewards what favors survival and reproduction: either one claims that they track independent moral truths — but selection has no reason to align the "advantageous" with the "true," and the relation remains scientifically implausible — or one admits that they were shaped independently of those truths — and then they offer no reliable access, and skepticism follows. From this Street derives not skepticism, but the abandonment of realism: value would not be an independent truth to be tracked, but an "attitude-dependent"

property, constituted by valuing creatures — this is metaethical constructivism, not to be confused with the rational construction of principles of Rawlsian descent, which remains among the tools of the method adopted here (cf. S. Street, "Constructivism about Reasons", 2008, and "What Is Constructivism in Ethics and Metaethics?", 2010). I assume the dilemma in its full force, without dodging it. But from it I do not draw, as Street does, the abandonment of realism: to declare value simply constructed would resolve the question in one direction, whereas what the dilemma establishes is only that intuitions, on their own, do not guarantee an independent truth — not that such a truth does not exist, nor that construction is the last word. The symmetry must then be honored to the end. Constructivism sees something realism tends to lose: that principles, and even the criteria by which we recognize a value, take shape in the process of mutual correction and are not found ready-made, waiting to be read off; that without valuing creatures the very question of what has value would have nowhere to arise. But realism sees what constructivism risks closing off: that at the end of that process there may be something not entirely ours, which scrutiny approaches instead of producing. The position assumed here does not choose between the two. If there truly were, at the end of the chain, an independent value, one would still reach it by constructing intuitions into principles and correcting them in dialogue: construction would not be the alternative to discovery, but its only route of access — and which of the two is at work remains undecidable from this side of that access.

[^5]: The trilemma is formulated by H. Albert, *Traktat über kritische Vernunft* (1968), who calls it the "Münchhausen trilemma": every justification falls into infinite regress, logical circle, or dogmatic halt. I read it not as proof of the impossibility of foundation, but as a description of the form an honest justification assumes once the claim to an ultimate foundation is abandoned.

[^6]: Here I take up, reversing its skeptical outcome, the structure of the trilemma: the three horns become three dimensions of a single movement of self-correction, none of which claims the status of ultimate justification. In relation to the great metaethical traditions, this reversal has a consequence: it allows one to welcome what each position sees, without welcoming its claim to be the only one. Intuitionism, and with it every absolutism of values, grasps a real fact — that before certain things recognition precedes argument, and that we sense within ourselves something like a moral conscience, a voice that reacts before any reasoning — but it absolutizes that datum, making it an infallible faculty that draws on truths already given, as if of them it could have a certainty it is not granted; the method retains its intuition as access, and strips it of infallibility by exposing it to scrutiny. Genealogical perspectivism, of Nietzschean descent, grasps that reasons refer backward to contingent forces, of nature and of history; but it absolutizes genealogy, turning it into a reduction — value would be only power or sediment — whereas the contingency of the origin does not cancel the fact that what has arisen from it can have value, and is judgeable. Constructivism grasps that principles take shape in the process of mutual correction, that they are not found ready-made; but it absolutizes the process, denying that it can approach something not entirely ours — this is the door that the horn of the circle instead leaves ajar. Coherentism, and in its most ambitious version Hegelian idealism, grasp that the true is systematic, that the whole holds together and that history has a direction; but idealism absolutizes this insight, making it a guaranteed necessity, and with it comes the temptation to redeem as a stage every moment of the path — whereas here the spiral remains fallible, can regress, and no advance redeems what it has trampled. Moral realism grasps that one halts because one recognizes something real, not only because one has grown tired of asking; but it absolutizes this recognition, claiming to exhibit the real as a certain foundation, whereas here the halt on something real remains a non-demonstrable possibility. Relativism grasps a true point, but places it at the wrong level. It sees that ethics does not speak from nowhere, that every judgment is born within a condition, a history, a form of life; but it concludes too quickly that every position holds only for the one who maintains it or for the culture that produces it. The relativity at play here is deeper and less dispersive: not primarily that of the individual or of the culture, but that, common to all, of the sentient and vulnerable condition. Ethics is situated because it speaks from within a life that can be wounded, deprived, recognized — not because it is consigned to the pure difference of opinions. It is a perspectival and epistemic relativity, concerning our access to value and the place from which it can appear as lived good or evil; not an ontological thesis about the nonexistence of independent values, which remains suspended like everything else. For this reason, from the situated character of ethics it does not follow that every position is as good as another: it follows that every position, including ours, speaks from within a condition it cannot leap over, but which, precisely because it is common, prevents perspective from becoming arbitrariness. The great normative ethics too enter this scheme from the side of method rather than that of foundation: Kantianism grasps the force of universalization, but treats it as a machine capable of

generating contents by itself, whereas it is a filter that works only when joined to what we access intuitively, and it tends of its own accord to harden into rules that do not look at consequences; utilitarianism grasps that consequences truly count, but absolutizes them, reducing to calculation even what calculation should not be able to touch. Two cautions prevent all this from lapsing into a syncretism that would give everyone their due. The first: the door left open is to the possible foundations of these positions, not to their claims of exclusivity, which scrutiny rejects; one welcomes what each sees, not its negation of the others. The second: since many of them are mutually incompatible — realism denies constructivism, absolutism denies relativism — the openness is not conjunctive but disjunctive: one does not hold open that they are all right together, which would be contradictory, but that some one of them grasps something true — as long as one remains honest about what we can know and what we cannot, and thus about the fact that which one is the truth cannot be established with certainty. Epistemic honesty and the dialogical structure of the method coincide here: the method does not choose one horn against the others, nor does it sum them; it holds them together as dimensions of a single searching, and precisely for this reason it can let each tradition speak without surrendering to any.

[^7]: On this point the text is in dialogue with the sensibility-based cognitivism of J. McDowell and D. Wiggins, according to which value is grasped in the relation between a situation and a formed sensibility, without being reduced to mere subjective projection or being given independently of every point of view. Here, however, the thesis remains more suspended and more epistemic: it is not decided whether what is grasped is an independent property, a construction of the living being, or something that emerges in the relation between living being and world; it is affirmed only that, in order to access value and recognize it as such, the relation between a world and a living being capable of being touched by it is required. Cf. J. McDowell, "Values and Secondary Qualities", in T. Honderich, ed., *Morality and Objectivity*, Routledge & Kegan Paul, 1985; D. Wiggins, "A Sensible Subjectivism?", in *Needs, Values, Truth: Essays in the Philosophy of Value*, Blackwell, 1987.

[^8]: On the terminological plane, the reference is to qualia, a term introduced into the contemporary philosophical lexicon by C. I. Lewis in *Mind and the World-Order: Outline of a Theory of Knowledge* (1929), to indicate the immediate qualitative characters of experience. The reference has no foundational function: it serves to specify that a living being that feels is not describable only from the outside, through functions, reactions, or physical correlates, but is a being for whom there is a way in which the world appears. Here one meets the so-called hard problem of consciousness, formulated by David Chalmers in "Facing Up to the Problem of Consciousness" (1995): not the problem, however difficult, of explaining how a system discriminates stimuli, integrates information, or produces behavior, but that of understanding why and how there is something that is felt from the inside. Thomas Nagel's formula in "What Is It Like to Be a Bat?" (1974) — what it is like to be a certain living being — remains, in this sense, one of the clearest ways of naming the subjective character of experience. The contemporary discussion remains open. Functionalist and neurocognitive theories such as Bernard Baars's Global Workspace Theory (*A Cognitive Theory of Consciousness*, 1988) and its neuroscientific reworking in the Global Neuronal Workspace Theory of Stanislas Dehaene and Jean-Pierre Changeux ("Experimental and Theoretical Approaches to Conscious Processing", 2011) understand consciousness as global access: a piece of information becomes conscious when it is stabilized and made available to multiple cognitive systems, such as memory, language, decision, and action control. Giulio Tononi's Integrated Information Theory ("An Information Integration Theory of Consciousness", 2004) links consciousness instead to the degree and structure of the integrated information in a system. Higher-order theories, such as those of David Rosenthal (*Consciousness and Mind*, 2005), explain consciousness through representations or thoughts directed at other mental states. Recurrent theories, such as Victor Lamme's ("Towards a True Neural Stance on Consciousness", 2006), insist on the role of reentrant circuits in conscious experience; predictive perspectives, such as those developed by Jakob Hohwy (*The Predictive Mind*, 2013) and Andy Clark (*Surfing Uncertainty*, 2016), interpret conscious perception within the framework of generative models, expectations, and error correction. Symbolic-self-referential models, such as Douglas Hofstadter's strange loop (*I Am a Strange Loop*, 2007), see the conscious self as an emergent structure of self-reference. Deflationist or illusionist positions, such as Daniel Dennett's (*Consciousness Explained*, 1991), contest instead that qualia, understood as private, ineffable, intrinsic properties, are coherent theoretical entities. Quantum or processual hypotheses, from John von Neumann (*Mathematical Foundations of Quantum Mechanics*, 1932) and Henry Stapp ("The Hard Problem: A Quantum Approach", 1995) up to the Orch-OR theory of Roger Penrose and Stuart Hameroff ("Consciousness in the Universe: A Review of the 'Orch OR' Theory", 2014), seek

finally a deeper link between consciousness, quantum measurement, cerebral microprocesses, and fundamental physical structure. Recent surveys, such as that of Anil Seth and Tim Bayne ("Theories of Consciousness", 2022), show precisely the plurality of the field and the difficulty of establishing which theory, if any, manages to explain together cognitive access, neural correlates, and the phenomenal character of experience. None of these perspectives, however, constitutes today a unanimously accepted solution. For this reason the reference to qualia does not claim to resolve the ultimate nature of consciousness, nor to ground value metaphysically. It indicates only the minimal phenomenological point from which this reflection sets out: for something to be able to present itself as good, evil, harm, or loss, there must be a center of experience for which the world does not simply happen, but gives itself in a lived way.

[^9]: That judgment interprets a valence already present in experience, without creating value from nothing, distinguishes this position both from strong subjectivism, for which value would be produced entirely by attitude, and from strong realism, when it understands value as an already complete property fully independent of any experiential access. S. Blackburn's quasi-realist expressivism (*Ruling Passions*, 1998) and A. Gibbard's norm-expressivism (*Wise Choices, Apt Feelings*, 1990) explain the grammar and practical force of moral judgments without committing to metaphysical moral properties: Blackburn shows how one can speak of truth, error, and practical objectivity starting from evaluative attitudes; Gibbard interprets normative judgment as the expression of the acceptance of norms. The point maintained here is different and more elementary: before moral judgment, before the normative statement or the acceptance of a norm, there is a lived valence, in which something already happens as good or bad for the one who lives it. This does not refute expressivism, but it prevents reducing all value to the level of judgment, of language, or of normative attitude.

[^10]: The distinction between the lived valence of experience and the moral obligation deriving from it takes account of the so-called "Hume's law": from how things are, or even from how they are lived, it does not follow by logic alone how one ought to act. The fact that something is bad-for-someone does not already contain, as a deductive conclusion, the norm that others ought to respect it. A further passage is needed. The necessity of the norm then takes the form of a reflective demand for recognition. It is not grounded on a single route, but is recognized and corroborated by several converging sources, which are then the same as those of the method: intersubjective recognition, by which what holds for me, as an exposed center of experience, I recognize as holding for the other as well; the contractualist form, by which a rule must be capable of being considered from every position involved and must not be reasonably rejectable; the constructivist moment, by which the norm takes shape in the process of universalization, correction, and dialogue; the analysis of effects, which shows what world such a norm makes possible; the logical coherence of the reasoning and of the principles on which it rests; and, at the root, the proto-evaluative source of the intuitions from which everything moves, which sink their origin into biology and culture, and perhaps — but this is a hypothesis on which judgment remains suspended — into a foundation of a metaphysical order. None of these sources, alone, deduces the norm; together, however, they positively posit it as necessary, not because they demonstrate it like a theorem, but because they sustain it as a reasoned recognition: revisable, and not for that reason arbitrary.

[^11]: One might object that a perfect and invulnerable being — and world — would have value in the highest degree, and that vulnerability is therefore not the root of value. The objection deserves to be taken seriously, and it must be granted that value does not rest on fragility alone. But looked at closely, the difficulty does not touch the thesis as much as it seems, and for several reasons. First of all, of invulnerability we have only a negative notion: we do not know it in itself, but only as the absence of what we are exposed to, being sheltered from every loss we can suffer. Of a good entirely unbound from the possibility of lacking we speak, in short, always from this side of our limit. Perhaps, moreover, the value that things have for us depends to some extent on our very vulnerability: it is our finitude that opens the possibility of losing what we hold dear, even when it is something that, in principle, is eternal and unassailable. There is then a sense in which vulnerability re-enters also from the side of a possible highest good: where it is understood not as a perfection closed in on itself, but as the source of a good turned toward the world, it binds itself to what in the world is vulnerable and can be wounded, and it holds to that world insofar as that world can fail it. This is the path of the dilemma formulated by H. Jonas (*Der Gottesbegriff nach Auschwitz*, 1984): of a good, omnipotent, and comprehensible God one cannot hold together all the predicates. If he is good but not omnipotent, what he wills in the world can be lost against his will, and he is in some way vulnerable in what he loves, a participant in the suffering of creation — the path Jonas himself takes. The other branch, that of an omnipotent and not good God, Jonas evokes while

thinking of Auschwitz; and already in its invulnerability is accompanied by a disvalue. But one can add that an omnipotent being, invulnerable in everything, from whom nothing can be taken and who has regard for nothing vulnerable, ceases for that very reason to appear to us as good, and is no longer distinguishable from indifference. There remains then the third side of the dilemma: that of an incomprehensible God, a good to which we simply have no access. We can try to imagine it — a full and eternal good, rejoicing in its own eternity while fearing nothing — but it is a good we cannot think except in relation to our exposure, and one which from our point of view risks blending into an indifferent immobility, in which a vulnerable world like ours would no longer have a place. Unless one thinks — and it is the hypothesis that speaks most to us, the exposed, without for that reason being more certain — that vulnerability itself is a good: not a privation, but the place where primary values such as love and freedom can be given, and thereby the possible metaphysical foundation of that value of vulnerability recognized here. But both remain hypotheses to which we have no access with any degree of certainty, and on which judgment must be suspended. One does not thereby demonstrate that vulnerability is the metaphysical condition of every possible value; one shows rather that, for vulnerable beings like us, the idea of an entirely invulnerable value remains uncertain: either it binds itself in any case to the vulnerable, or it becomes incomprehensible, or it risks appearing as indifference. And of the existence, as of the absence, of such a being, or of such a good, we can have no certainty, and it is more honest to admit it. What the dilemma shows, then, is not that value cannot exist without vulnerability, but that value as it is given to us does not let itself be separated from it.

[^12]: In this sense the position may be called sentientist, but only in a qualified form. It shares with sentientism the idea that moral consideration cannot depend on species membership, but on the presence of a center of experience: where there is someone capable of feeling, suffering, enjoying, or being deprived of goods of their own, there is already someone for whom what happens can go well or badly. It is the nucleus that, in utilitarian form, is found in Peter Singer: the capacity to suffer and to have interests is what makes a being morally considerable, and like interests must receive equal consideration, regardless of species. Cf. P. Singer, *Animal Liberation*, 1975; *Practical Ethics*, 1979. The path proposed here, however, does not coincide with Singer's. First of all, sentience is not assumed only as a capacity to have interests to be included in an impartial utilitarian calculus, but as a center of access to value: the point at which the world can appear as lived good or evil. From here no complete morality is deduced, nor is an absolute value of the sentient simply postulated; it is rather recognized, through the method described so far, that where there is experience there is someone for whom what happens can matter. Consequences remain decisive, but they do not exhaust judgment: they enter into relation with dignity, care, vulnerability, the confrontation with other values, and the moral residue. For this reason the sentientism defended here is more elastic and articulated than a purely utilitarian position: it does not reduce everything to the minimization of suffering, but recognizes in sentient life a strong moral threshold, which judgment must each time cross with caution, without transforming it either into a blind absolute or into an element simply available to calculation. From this also follows a distinction that is missing, or remains less central, in many forms of sentientism: that between moral status and profile of goods. Sentience opens the threshold of consideration; the form of life determines which goods are at stake and what harm can be suffered. Thus one avoids both speciesism, which arbitrarily excludes or devalues animals, and an undifferentiated egalitarianism, which does not distinguish between different forms of experience, relation, memory, future, and loss. Every sentient being counts; it does not follow that every harm weighs the same, nor that every conflict is resolved through a single measure. It is significant that even a Kantian thinker such as Christine Korsgaard, though starting from different premises, recognizes in sentient animals beings for whom something can be good or bad. The convergence is strong: here too the value of the sentient is not simply attributed from outside, but recognized starting from the fact that there exist living beings for whom the world can go one way or another. The difference concerns above all the theoretical path: Korsgaard reconstructs this recognition within a Kantian framework of practical rationality; here, instead, it is placed within a broader, fallible, and pluralist method, which assumes feeling as the decisive threshold of value without making it the only morally relevant good. An analogous but more cautious theoretical move is made in the following note with respect to the non-sentient living being: just as Korsgaard shows, from a Kantian framework, that sentient animals too have a good of their own, here it is recognized that non-sentient life too can have value, though without coinciding with the strong moral status of one who feels. Cf. also T. Regan, *The Case for Animal Rights*, 1983; C. Korsgaard, *Fellow Creatures*, 2018; M. C. Nussbaum, *Justice for Animals*, 2023.

[^13]: An open question remains: if sentience fixes moral status in the proper sense, what of the value of that which lives without, perhaps, feeling? The vitalist theses grasp something important here. Schweitzer, when he speaks of the "life that wills to live," understands life as an elementary will to persevere in its own existence; Taylor, when he describes every organism as a "teleological center of life," sees in the living being a system oriented toward its own good, its own conservation, and its own flourishing; Jonas, when he interprets metabolism as the originary form of self-affirmation, shows the living being as that which must continually maintain itself against its own dissolution. In different ways, these positions indicate a real trait: non-sentient life is not mere inert matter, nor simple available material. An organism grows, conserves itself, tends toward its own form, can be favored or damaged; in this sense it possesses a good of its own. But precisely here the decisive objection arises. To say that a living being tends toward its own maintenance describes a fact; to say that this tending has value already introduces an evaluative attribute. If such value is understood as an objective property inscribed in life itself, then one enters a metaphysical thesis difficult to demonstrate, or a postulate that biological description alone does not prove. And, in any case, the fact of assuming it as moral recognition depends implicitly on a human evaluative intuition: the intuition that life has value in itself. This intuition should not be discarded, because it grasps something; but neither can it stand alone as ultimate foundation. It must be confronted with another intuition, of a different level: that a center of experience has a more radical value, because it is not merely something to which we attribute value, but the very place where value can appear as lived good or evil. A sentient being is the point at which the world and value are not only described from outside: they happen for someone. In this sense the center of experience has a transcendental, or meta-level, priority: it is the condition for something to be able to present itself as value. But this priority concerns access, not yet the value of the sentient: to say that without a center of experience nothing would appear as good or evil is not equivalent to saying that the sentient has value. The first is a trait of how value is accessible to us; the second is a recognition — that a being for whom things go well or badly cannot be treated as if nothing happened to it — and it does not follow from the first by deduction. In non-sentient life one can recognize a value as organized, fragile, unrepeatable form, as part of an ecosystem and a condition of the life of other beings; but this value does not coincide with the strong moral status of one who feels, because it does not present, at least as far as we can recognize, that internal point of view for which the world is lived as good or evil. Sentience remains the threshold of moral status in the strong sense, because only where there is experience is there someone for whom the world can go well or badly from within. There remains, then, the difference that egalitarian vitalism risks erasing: that between what can be damaged and who can be wounded. Cf. A. Schweitzer, *Kulturphilosophie* (1923); P. W. Taylor, *Respect for Nature* (1986); H. Jonas, *Organism and Freedom* (1966). For the opposite risk of ecological holism, cf. A. Leopold, *A Sand County Almanac* (1949): the value of the ecosystem may weigh heavily, but it should not absorb without residue the value of the individual sentient being. In tragic cases, the continuity of a form of life or of a broader equilibrium can come into conflict with the protection of the individual; but even when judgment recognizes the necessity of the loss, it cannot be entirely absorbed by the good that justifies it: a moral residue remains.

[^14]: The norm, as has been said, is not deduced mechanically from lived valence, but is posited through a reasoned recognition supported by several converging sources: intuition, universalization, coherence, consequences, dialogue, justifiability. Here a further point must be specified: this passage concerns moral agents, that is, those who can understand reasons, assume obligations, answer for their actions; but the norm they recognize does not hold only toward other moral agents. It holds also toward moral patients: beings that may not be able to formulate a norm, to contract, to promise, or to make claims, but for whom what we do can become lived good or evil. This distinction prevents reducing morality to an agreement between symmetrical subjects. A certain contractualist tradition tends in fact to think justice starting from subjects capable of cooperating, contracting, and reciprocating; in this form, however, it risks leaving at the margins precisely those who do not possess, do not yet possess, no longer possess, or possess only fragily those capacities. The problem does not concern a marginal case: infancy, illness, severe disability, dependence, temporary or permanent loss of cognitive faculties show that moral vulnerability does not coincide with rational autonomy. It is the limit that Martha Nussbaum identifies in contractualist theories founded on reciprocity among equals, when she observes that they tend to place the disabled, animals, and severely dependent persons "at the frontiers of justice." Cf. J. Rawls, *A Theory of Justice*, 1971; D. Gauthier, *Morals by Agreement*, 1986; E. F. Kittay, *Love's Labor*, 1999; A. MacIntyre, *Dependent Rational Animals*, 1999; M. C. Nussbaum, *Frontiers of Justice*, 2006. The criterion of justifiability must then be understood not as an actual pact among those who have a voice, but as a test to which a norm must submit with respect to all the positions it involves. In this

direction one can also read T. M. Scanlon's contractualism, by which a norm must be justifiable before others and not reasonably rejectable by those it involves (*What We Owe to Each Other*, 1998), though the problem remains open of those who cannot fully participate in the discursive exchange. The decisive point, here, is that the impossibility of formulating an objection does not equal the absence of a morally relevant interest. Those who cannot speak can nevertheless suffer; and if they can suffer in the first person, the norm concerning them must answer for them too. The formula is thus this: the norm arises among moral agents, but it does not hold only toward moral agents. It holds toward all moral patients, that is, toward all centers of experience for whom what we do can be lived as harm, care, deprivation, protection, or abandonment. Rational capacities remain decisive for establishing who can be responsible for obligations; they cannot, however, be the sole threshold for establishing who can be their beneficiary. If it were so, the loss of speech, of autonomy, or of rationality would diminish the very title to moral consideration precisely when the need for protection increases.

[^15]: Fundamental rights can be understood as the public and institutional translation of certain moral recognitions matured historically: that a person cannot be reduced to a thing, that their life is not at the disposal of another's arbitrary will, that power must meet limits before the vulnerability of those who can suffer it. In this sense they do not constitute an ultimate foundation of ethics, but one of its historical forms of stabilization: they transform certain moral constraints into public claims, opposable to those who govern, to those who judge, to those who dispose of force, and sometimes even to the majority itself. The language of rights thus makes it possible to say not only that something would be good or just, but that someone can claim it as owed. The theoretical genealogies of rights are multiple. The tradition of natural law and natural rights, from Grotius, Pufendorf, and Locke to the modern revolutionary declarations, has maintained that certain rights belong to the human being as such, prior to positive recognition by the State. In Pufendorf, for example, dignity is already linked to the reciprocal recognition of a moral status between beings capable of addressing claims to one another; in Locke the rights to life, liberty, and property precede political power and delimit its legitimacy. The Kantian tradition shifts the center of gravity to the dignity of the person as a rational and free being, to be treated always also as an end and never merely as a means; from here derives one of the most influential matrices of the modern language of dignity. The contractualist and republican traditions have instead insisted on the necessity that power be justifiable before those over whom it is exercised, and that freedom be protected from arbitrary will. In the twentieth century, after the crisis of merely state-based guarantees and the experience of the totalitarianisms, the language of rights took on a more explicitly international form: no longer only the rights of the citizen within a State, but the rights of the human being even against the State. These genealogies, however, do not fully coincide. Natural law tends to seek a foundation anterior to positive law; Kantianism grounds dignity on rationality and autonomy; contractualism ties it to reciprocal justifiability; theories of interests, of basic needs, and of capabilities insist instead on what a human life needs in order not to be crushed in its concrete vulnerability. The point is not to choose one of these genealogies as the only true one, nor to line them up side by side as if they were simply compatible. Each sees something and risks losing something else. Natural law reminds us that power does not create the just by itself, but risks transforming into an eternal datum what is also a historical conquest. Legal positivism reminds us that a right, in order truly to protect, must take institutional form, but risks leaving the just at the mercy of the law in force. Kantianism sees forcefully that the person cannot be treated as a means, but can restrict dignity too much by tying it to full rationality. Contractualism shows that a norm must be justifiable before others, but must be corrected when it imagines only autonomous, symmetrical subjects capable of speech. The ethics of care and of dependence bring back to the center what these theories tend to leave in the background: the fact that all autonomy is sustained, exposed, vulnerable. Theories of needs and capabilities add that dignity is not only formal inviolability, but the concrete possibility of living, acting, speaking, participating. The method followed here works precisely in this space of reciprocal correction. It starts from elementary moral intuitions but does not leave them in their immediacy. It subjects them to universalization, coherence, consequences, historical comparison, and the listening to those who have suffered exclusion or domination. Thus one genealogy corrects another: natural law prevents positivism from identifying law with justice; positivism reminds natural law that a claim without institutions remains fragile; Kantianism limits calculation; consequences prevent the principle from becoming blind; contractualism demands justifiability; care and dependence widen that justifiability to those who cannot defend themselves; capabilities show whether the proclaimed right corresponds truly to a possible life. Their modern normative formulation is born of a precise history. The eighteenth-century declarations — the American Declaration of Independence of 1776, the French Declaration of the Rights of Man and of the Citizen of 1789 — universalize in political form the language of natural rights, but remain marked by exclusions and historical

limits. After the Second World War, the United Nations Charter of 1945 reaffirms faith in fundamental rights, in the dignity and worth of the human person; the Universal Declaration of Human Rights of 1948 then proclaims, in its preamble, that the recognition of the inherent dignity and of the equal and inalienable rights of all members of the human family is the foundation of freedom, justice, and peace in the world. The reference to the "barbarous acts" that have outraged the conscience of humankind shows the historical and negative character of this universalization: rights are formulated not only from a theory of the human good, but also from the memory of what happens when the human being is made juridically, politically, or materially disposable. In 1966, with the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights and the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights, that declaration took on a more articulated treaty-based and juridical form, constituting with them the so-called International Bill of Human Rights. In the Italian context, the same nucleus is recognized by art. 2 of the Constitution, according to which the Republic "recognizes and guarantees the inviolable rights of man," both as an individual and within the social formations in which his personality unfolds. In this sense fundamental rights do not close the question of the ultimate foundation. They are truths with a lowercase "t": historically posited, juridically recognized, revisable in formulation and application, but not arbitrary. They derive neither from a single theory nor from a simple convention: they gather moral intuitions, reasons, consequences, historical experiences, and struggles for recognition. They fix public thresholds below which human life is exposed to violence, arbitrariness, humiliation, or abandonment. They do not by themselves ground dignity, but they make it enforceable. Cf. H. Grotius, *De iure belli ac pacis*, 1625; S. Pufendorf, *De jure naturae et gentium*, 1672; J. Locke, *Second Treatise of Government*, 1689; I. Kant, *Groundwork of the Metaphysics of Morals*, 1785, and *The Metaphysics of Morals*, 1797; H. Arendt, *The Origins of Totalitarianism*, 1951; J. Rawls, *A Theory of Justice*, 1971, and *The Law of Peoples*, 1999; R. Dworkin, *Taking Rights Seriously*, 1977; J. Donnelly, *Universal Human Rights in Theory and Practice*, 1989; M. C. Nussbaum, *Frontiers of Justice*, 2006; A. Sen, *The Idea of Justice*, 2009; C. Beitz, *The Idea of Human Rights*, 2009; J. Nickel, "Human Rights", *Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy*.

[^16]: "Threshold deontology" designates the position according to which certain deontological constraints are not simply absorbed by the calculation of consequences: certain actions remain forbidden even if they would produce an ordinary positive balance; however, in the face of sufficiently grave consequences, the constraint may yield. The position thus attempts to avoid two extremes: on one side integral consequentialism, willing to sacrifice the individual whenever the overall balance requires it; on the other absolute deontology, incapable of recognizing the weight of moral catastrophes or extreme harms. This form of mediation is discussed, among others, by T. Nagel, R. Nozick, L. Alexander, and M. S. Moore. The main problem is that the threshold risks appearing arbitrary: if the constraint yields before a thousand lives saved, why not before nine hundred and ninety-nine? If it is mobile, by what criterion does it move? If it is fixed, why exactly there? To this difficulty is added the problem of aggregation: it is not obvious how to sum harms suffered by different persons without erasing the fact that each harm is lived by someone in the first person; and yet refusing all aggregation would make it impossible to explain why certain catastrophes weigh more than limited harms. Precisely for this reason I use threshold deontology in a tempered, non-mathematical form. I do not mean that there exists an exact quantity of consequences capable of "buying" the violation of dignity; I mean that the constraint is not blind to real effects, but that effects never transform a life into available material. The threshold, here, is not a number: it is a zone of tragic deliberation, in which judgment must answer at once for the constraint, for the consequences, for the moral residue, and for the impossibility of resolving the conflict as if it were pure calculation. Cf. T. Nagel, "War and Massacre" (1972); R. Nozick, *Anarchy, State, and Utopia* (1974); L. Alexander, "Deontology at the Threshold" (2000); M. S. Moore, "The Rationality of Threshold Deontology" (2019); A. Ellis, "Deontology, Incommensurability and the Arbitrary" (1992).

[^17]: The threshold/profile distinction is the cornerstone of the position. Moral status is binary: sentience opens consideration; it either is or is not there. The profile of goods is gradual and depends on the form of life. This makes it possible to hold together the equal considerability of every sentient being and the concrete difference in what, for each, is at stake. In this sense I accept the variability of the harm of death according to psychological continuity, discussed by J. McMahan in *The Ethics of Killing* (2002), as a thesis about the profile of goods, not about status: the weight of the harm can vary without the dignity of the one who suffers it varying. It is the point at which I part from the more gradualist conclusions about status.

[^18]: On the fact that dependence generates more demanding obligations, and not a title to dispose, the position approaches the ethics of care and responsibility; I recall above all the idea, of Jonasian origin (H. Jonas, *Das Prinzip Verantwortung*, 1979), that power over a vulnerable being grounds proportionate responsibility, not right. The principle fixes the direction of the constraint, not its measure: it says that obligations grow with dependence, not how far they reach in the cases where dependence is maximal and institutionalized. How much it weighs on those practices, and whether it is compatible with some form of use, is a question that exceeds the foundation and that here I can only leave open.

[^19]: Concrete potentiality is to be understood within the same framework. Not every future possibility has the same moral weight: that a being could, in the abstract, become something does not yet mean that it already possesses now all the goods, relations, and forms of experience proper to what it will become. If abstract possibility sufficed to ground status, then moral value would no longer depend on what a being already is — on its experience, its vulnerability, the goods already in development — but on what it could become in favorable conditions. The risk would be to transform every biological or technical possibility into a full moral title, blurring the difference between an actual subject, a developing sentient living being, and a possibility not yet actualized. Different is the case in which certain dimensions are already rooted in a sentient living being, even if not yet fully developed. In the newborn, for example, it is not a generic future that grounds status, already opened by sentience; it is the presence of a living being included in the space of experience, vulnerability, and care, with developing goods that can be safeguarded or compromised. Potentiality, then, does not replace actual status: it accompanies it when it is rooted in what the being already is, in its form of life and in the concrete continuity of the goods that can develop or be protected. For this reason it must be distinguished from the arguments that transform mere potential into an immediate title to already full rights. The point here is not to treat specific questions such as abortion, the beginning of personal life, or end-of-life conflicts, which would require an autonomous discussion; it is only to clarify that, within this framework, the future counts morally when it is not an abstract possibility separated from present status, but the concrete continuation of a life already involved in the space of experience, vulnerability, and care. Cf. J. McMahan, *The Ethics of Killing: Problems at the Margins of Life*, Oxford University Press, 2002; E. Harman, "The Potentiality Problem", *Philosophical Studies* 114, nos. 1–2, 2003.

[^20]: This note does not treat the topic of euthanasia, but delimits the point at which the threshold proposed here meets the case of the will to die. The thesis that, in extreme conditions and according to the free, competent, and current judgment of the person themselves, the continuation of life can be lived as the greater evil — to the point that further life no longer appears, to the one living it, as a possible good — is maintained, on different bases, by P. Foot ("Euthanasia", 1977) and J. McMahan (*The Ethics of Killing*, 2002, ch. 2). The position assumed here does not derive from it any right to dispose of another's life: it distinguishes the case in which death is inflicted on a person for an external end — always excluded by the threshold — from that in which it is the person themselves who recognizes, from their own point of view, that continuing is the greater evil. For the second case to be what it claims, and not a counterfeit of it, the will must be current, competent, free from coercion, and not the transitory effect of unrelieved suffering or of abandonment: requirements whose ascertainment is inseparable from a context of care, and which distinguish the request of one who no longer wants to live from that, quite different, of one who no longer wants to live *like this*. Against the Kantian objection that choosing one's own death would violate rational dignity (D. Velleman, "A Right of Self-Termination?", 1999), I follow the argument that assisting one who lucidly chooses not to prolong intolerable suffering does not treat them as a means, but as an end that counts for its own sake (cf. McMahan, *The Ethics of Killing*). The distinction stands firm between voluntary euthanasia, grounded in the current and competent will of the person, and the cases in which that will cannot be expressed. Where the person manifested it earlier, when they could — in advance directives — it is still their choice that holds, however much pronounced in the past. Where instead no will exists to lean on, the structure described here does not extend by analogy: there is no longer a subject making the threshold count from within, and every decision taken by others risks turning into what the threshold forbids, namely disposing of a life from the outside. In these cases the possible substituted judgment is not an application of the criterion, but its extreme and fragile approximation, bound to the sole good of the subject, surrounded by the greatest guarantees, and burdened with a residue that no procedure erases. The renunciation of therapeutic obstinacy — the distinction between proportionate and disproportionate means of life support — belongs to a plane that concerns medical deontology. The case of

euthanasia, in all its forms, being a delicate and complex topic, clearly deserves a very thorough treatment that cannot be given here.

[^21]: The "experience machine" thought experiment is R. Nozick's, *Anarchy, State, and Utopia* (1974): if we refuse to plug into a machine that would give us only pleasant states, then we do not want only to feel pleasure, but to be in contact with reality, to do, to bind ourselves. It is an argument against hedonism as the sole measure of the good.

[^22]: The objection to negative utilitarianism — that if the absence of suffering were assumed as the sole criterion, one would arrive at the paradoxical outcome whereby eliminating suffering by eliminating the sufferers would appear as the supreme good — is discussed starting from R. N. Smart, "Negative Utilitarianism" (1958). It shows that the absence of pain cannot be the sole criterion.

[^23]: In the case of AI, at least in its current state, it remains uncertain whether there is internal experience in the proper sense. As recalled in note 8, the point is not only whether a system performs certain functions or manifests certain behavioral dispositions, but whether there is something that is felt from the inside. Artificial systems can produce evaluative language, simulate preferences, express aversion or consent, but it is not clear that anything happens *for* them as pain, loss, desire, or lived good. Recent literature invites us not to dismiss the problem as science fiction: Butlin, Long, and others propose evaluating artificial systems in the light of the main scientific theories of consciousness, through functional indicators; their conclusion is that no current system turns out to be conscious, while there are no obvious technical barriers to future systems satisfying some of the indicators. Chalmers, discussing large language models, considers it unlikely that current LLMs are conscious, but maintains that the possibility must be taken seriously for subsequent systems. More recently, Long, Sebo, Butlin, Birch, and Chalmers have defended a precautionary position on AI welfare: not because current systems are certainly moral patients, but because uncertainty about consciousness, robust agency, and possible moral relevance could become practically important. Cf. P. Butlin et al., "Consciousness in Artificial Intelligence: Insights from the Science of Consciousness" (2023); D. Chalmers, "Could a Large Language Model be Conscious?" (2023); R. Long et al., "Taking AI Welfare Seriously" (2024). Within the framework of this note, however, the decisive point is a further one. AI, even when it manipulates moral contents, does not show that it has pathic access to value: it does not seem to start from lived evaluative intuitions, from a vulnerability of its own, from a pain or a joy that would open for it the field of good and evil. It can treat value as linguistic, inferential, or decisional content; it is not clear that it can encounter it as something that concerns it from within. In sentient living beings, moreover, evaluative intuition has an embodied genealogy: it arises from a biological, affective, and relational history of exposure to the world. All of this roots it in a process that, whatever ultimate origin — chance, necessity, or design — one wishes to attribute to it, remains ancestrally part of us; without this by itself demonstrating its validity, as the path of the text has tried to show. AI does not inherit this origin: it can simulate judgments, preferences, and moral reasoning, but it does not have behind it a lived history that has left deep traces in it. For this reason intelligence is not enough, nor is linguistic competence, nor the capacity to reason about norms, to automatically open strong moral status. If one day there were serious reasons to attribute to an artificial system an internal experience — not only intelligent behavior, but a point of view for which something can go well or badly — then the criterion proposed here would impose caution. Until then, AI remains above all an epistemic limit-case: it shows why the center of ethics cannot be rationality or language alone, but lived access to value.

[^24]: The principle of caution in the face of uncertainty about sentience inverts the burden of proof: where there are serious reasons to suppose an experience, it is exclusion, not inclusion, that must justify itself. It holds above all for animals whose inner life is difficult to interpret: species distant from us, forms of sensibility not immediately recognizable, affective states not superimposable on ours. Uncertainty does not authorize treating them as things; on the contrary, precisely because we cannot access their lived experience directly, moral prudence must weigh on the side of those who could be wounded. This does not imply, however, that every human relation with animals is reducible to domination. There are forms of coexistence, care, husbandry, and work in which the asymmetry remains real but does not exhaust everything that happens: the animal can receive protection, nourishment, shelter, care, relational continuity, and sometimes a safer life than it would have in conditions of natural exposure. Precisely because it remains asymmetric, however, the relation does not absolve the use: it charges it with responsibility. The more an animal is made dependent on us, the more the duty toward its effective welfare grows. Concrete conditions can modulate the way in which the constraint is honored, not

the animal's status. An animal that feels remains someone, in the minimal and decisive sense that there exists a point of view for which things can go well or badly; if, in certain historical and material situations, that constraint is not honored fully, what remains is not a full permission, but a residue. Here the distinction between threshold and profile of goods proves useful again. The threshold is not graduated: where there is experience, there is someone who counts and who cannot be treated as a thing. What varies is the profile of what can be protected or lost. Different forms of life are exposed to different goods and harms: bonds, memory, exploration, play, learning, social continuity, movement, safety, freedom from fear, and the possibility of species-typical behaviors can carry different weight according to the animal involved. In this sense some harms can be less grave than others, not because the one who suffers them counts less, but because what is actually wounded, deprived, or lost differs. The profile of goods thus orients care and the evaluation of harm, not the value of the living being nor its availability. This holds also in limit cases, such as the control of animals or insects that are vectors of grave diseases. In such situations, destructive intervention can be justified by the concurrence of several factors: the uncertainty about the presence and form of subjective experience, the gravity of the harm avoided to certainly sentient beings, sanitary necessity, the proportion of the means, and the absence of equally effective alternatives. But even here the justification does not arise from the idea that this living being is pure moral nothingness, nor from the fact that a less accessible profile of goods makes it simply sacrificable. It arises from the extreme character of the conflict. For this reason, even when the intervention is justified, a moral residue remains: not necessarily a prohibition, but the duty not to transform necessity into indifference, to limit the harm to what is necessary, and to prefer, where they exist, less destructive means. This is particularly relevant for animal husbandry. Not every form of husbandry is morally identical: industrial practices founded on extreme confinement, systematic suffering, and the reduction of the animal to a productive unit are much harder to defend than forms in which the animal lives in conditions of movement, care, relation, and lesser suffering. Here too, however, the distinction does not cancel the constraint: it can make a practice less unjust, more proportionate, perhaps in certain contexts still tolerable, but it does not automatically transform a sentient life into an available means. The weight of human needs must also be considered. In some contexts animal consumption may be tied to survival, food security, or the concrete absence of alternatives; here need weighs far more than preference, taste, or habit. Different is the case in which the use of the animal is sustained above all by convenience, luxury, tradition, or cultural inertia. Tradition is not morally null: it can preserve knowledge, local economies, relations, and shared forms of life; but it never suffices, on its own, to justify the harm it produces, and it becomes moral inertia when it uses its own antiquity to evade the revision of that harm. For this reason the balance must hold together sentience, suffering, the quality of the relation, effective welfare, human-produced dependence, the necessity of the end, the available alternatives, the social and cultural weight of the practice, and the moral residue. The residue does not automatically forbid every practice; it prevents, however, normalizing it as if nothing were at stake. It obliges one to reduce the harm, to distinguish necessity from habit, to improve conditions, and to orient oneself, where possible, toward forms less violent and less blind to the animal's life.

[^25]: The pluralism of values in conflict is I. Berlin's thesis (*Four Essays on Liberty*, 1969); the irreducible plurality of moral goods and the possibility of conflicting *prima facie* duties goes back to W. D. Ross (*The Right and the Good*, 1930). Incommensurability does not imply relativism: it concerns only the goods that have already passed the scrutiny. Something similar holds also on the plane of rights, but with a decisive specification: fundamental rights are not just any goods translated into juridical form; they are public claims that protect goods dependent on the threshold of dignity. For this reason they can come into conflict and require balancing, but they are not available in the same sense in which ordinary interests are. Balancing concerns the concrete profile of the right — modes, limits, conditions of exercise, relations with other rights — not its essential core. One point, in fact, remains withheld: the reduction of a person to a mere thing, used as a means for an end that is not their own. On this, positions diverge. M. S. Moore would bring it back within the logic of the threshold, where even the strongest constraint can yield before extreme consequences ("The Rationality of Threshold Deontology", 2019; cf. note 16); A. Gewirth recognizes in it instead an absolute that no balance can redeem, a right not to be annihilated as the object of another's end ("Are There Any Absolute Rights?", 1981); F. M. Kamm shows the point of truth in both demands, insisting on the fact that inviolability does not depend only on the quantity of harm produced, but on the type of action performed: a person of whom everything were weighable would be, precisely for that reason, less inviolable (*Intricate Ethics*, 2007). The dispute can be traversed without introducing a second starting point: the normativity of rights descends from dignity, and with it carries its threshold. In extreme tragic cases, where the conflict seems to compel crossing that threshold, the

point is not to seek the balance that would transform the sacrifice into something licit. The value trampled is not converted into permission: it persists as residue. Hence the decisive distinction between grounding in advance the lawfulness of the act and evaluating afterward, possibly, its excusability. The judgment of the Bundesverfassungsgericht on the German aviation security law (Luftsicherheitsgesetz) shows this structure with particular clarity: the State cannot authorize the shooting down of a hijacked plane with innocent passengers on board in order to save other lives on the ground, because this would mean treating those passengers as mere instruments. The prohibition does not eliminate the tragedy of the case, but it prevents the tragic from becoming an ordinary criterion of lawfulness. The possible act performed in an extreme situation is thus not transformed into a right: it can at most open, on the penal plane, the question of personal excusability, which the prevailing doctrine frames as an excusing state of necessity — the act remains unlawful, and what falls away is only the personal reproach (BVerfG, 15 February 2006, 1 BvR 357/05). The same scheme surfaces in Italian constitutional law and in European law, through the idea of a core or essence of rights. The Italian Constitutional Court has spoken of an "irreducible core" of the right to health as an "inviolable domain of human dignity," withdrawn even from the weight of financial exigencies (judgments nos. 304/1994 and 309/1999); art. 52, para. 1, of the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union requires that every limitation respect the essence of rights, and in the same direction points the guarantee of the essential content in art. 19, para. 2, of the German Basic Law (on the debate around this "essence," O. Scarcello, "Preserving the 'Essence' of Fundamental Rights under Article 52(1) of the Charter", 2021; for the reading according to which fundamental values are not "subject to balancing," K. Lenaerts). Below that core one does not weigh: one refuses. But here too certainty is not absolute: what is inviolable is the content of the core, not our grasp of it. Where exactly it passes remains a matter of fallible judgment, case by case.

[^26]: On the fact that the value sacrificed in a tragic choice persists as moral residue — and not as a mere cost — the reference is to B. Williams ("Ethical Consistency", 1965) and R. Marcus ("Moral Dilemmas and Consistency", 1980). The right choice can leave a debt; it is the sign that the conflict was real.

[^27]: This knot — why the recognition of the just does not translate by itself into reality — is the point at which ethics collides with the way things actually go in the world. That relations of domination are not first of all errors of judgment, but material structures that reproduce themselves and shape the consciousness of those immersed in them, is the nucleus of K. Marx's thought: it is not consciousness that determines social being, but social being that determines consciousness (*A Contribution to the Critique of Political Economy*, 1859). From it I draw a corrective to the intellectualism inherent in every ethics, the illusion that arguing well is enough for an unjust arrangement to change. I do not, however, assume materialism in the strong form according to which moral ideas would be a mere reflection of the relations of production. If it were so, the critique of domination would have no other argumentation than that of one interest opposed to another interest. Material relations can shape consciousness, orient what appears natural, and render suffering invisible; but they do not erase the fact that this suffering is suffered by someone, nor the possibility that from there judgment can open. The question, moreover, is deeper: domination operates not only by repressing, but by producing what appears natural to each, and the most stable power is the one that obtains the consent of those who undergo it — the lesson linking M. Foucault (*Discipline and Punish*, 1975) to A. Gramsci's hegemony (*Prison Notebooks*). To this external grip an internal one is added: faced with the contradiction between what it does and what it holds to be just, the mind tends to realign its convictions rather than its conduct — the mechanism psychology has called cognitive dissonance (L. Festinger, 1957) — and thus does not see what would oblige it to change. Nothing assures us that what is just, in the long run, prevails: often it does not prevail, and domination endures. But the suffering of those who undergo it does not disappear, however much an order makes it appear normal. Most of the time that pain does not manage to crack anything: it is absorbed, silenced, forgotten. And yet it can always, at a certain point, resurface and shake the order that produces it, and it is on this possibility that all change is staked. In this margin power shows another possible face. Bound to a statute of rights recognized to each, it can cease to be only what threatens the vulnerable and become what protects them; and conflict, within that frame, can cease to be oppression and become the form in which different needs measure themselves against one another without the weakest being annihilated — not conflict in itself, but the conflict made possible by a threshold of rights (it is in this direction, from a perspective attentive to concrete capabilities, that A. Sen moves, *Development as Freedom*, 1999). How the just manages to give itself a body in the world — with what force, within what relations, overcoming what resistances — is a complex and open question. And to this uncertainty about making it happen a more radical one is added, concerning it from within: the orientation never possesses the

certainty of having seen rightly, however much, as we have said, it is not arbitrary. It proceeds by revisable approximations, and what today seems an advance may tomorrow prove to be another, better-masked error. The truths it arrives at remain lowercase: fallible, revisable, never certain. Nothing guarantees it that the direction is the right one, and not merely the one visible from where it stands. But it is no small thing to admit fallibility while still taking a position. And to maintain an open attitude, and a coherent tension toward more sustainable, habitable, and balanced forms.

[^28]: The argument that whoever seriously advances an objection already recognizes a minimal normative space takes up, in cautious form, the pragmatic transcendental argumentation of K.-O. Apel and J. Habermas. I do not claim that it refutes the coherent nihilist: it delimits what can present itself as a rational objection, distinguishing it from the pure exercise of power.

[^29]: The reply to Nietzsche does not deny the power of the genealogy, but contests its status as fact: it is interpretation, not demonstration. The rereading of care as a form of strength, and not as the reaction of the weak, owes much to those who have read in Nietzsche himself (cf. B. Reginster, *The Affirmation of Life*, 2006) affirmation as the measuring of oneself against resistance, not as domination.

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